

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The article describes comparative examples of a number of scientific studies on the etiological causes and mechanisms of pathogenetic development, clinical course of the disease and modern diagnostic methods in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis who undergo scientific research. The article also comprehensively studies the general clinical characteristics of chronic rhinosinusitis, the compatibility and differential changes in laboratory and instrumental research data, the results and consequences of the disease, and positively evaluates the studied clinical results and achievements with completely new and qualified approaches to effective treatment.*

Keywords: *chronic rhinosinusitis, paranasal sinus disease, chronic rhinitis, inflammation of the nasal mucosa.*

Etiopathogenesis. Inflammatory diseases of the nasal cavities in children are considered as a polyetiological disease of the whole body. Acute sinusitis often occurs as a result of an acute infectious disease: viral infection of the respiratory tract, influenza, measles, rubella and other diseases, activation of secondary microflora (mainly highly pathogenic staphylococci, less streptococci and their combinations, mixed viral-bacterial infection, blue bacillus and Escherichia coli, proteus, enterococci, Frenkel diplococci, Friedlander pneumobacilli).

Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) occurs mainly under the influence of monoflora or due to the combination of viral microorganisms with saprophytes. As a result of the widespread use of various antibiotics, the biological properties of microorganisms have changed significantly, and antibiotic-resistant forms have appeared. If the growth of microorganisms is not observed in the inoculation of pus from the sinuses, then an aseptic inflammatory process, allergic diseases, viral infection, anaerobic microflora, or α -hemolytic streptococci can be detected, forming Z-form not detected in normal nutrient medium.

According to a number of foreign authors, the main causative agents of acute rhinosinusitis in children include the following pathogenic microflora: hemophilus influenzae, moraxella catarrhalis and streptococcus pneumoniae, staphylococcus sp., streptococcus sp. - aerobic and escherichia coli, proteus vulgaris and pseudomonas aeruginosa - anaerobic microorganisms are the cause.

At the same time, it is important to recognize that influenza and parainfluenza rhinoviruses, as well as parainfluenza and adenoviruses have been isolated in the relapses of acute and chronic rhinosinusitis developed on the basis of many respiratory viral diseases.

In case of staphylococcal infection, the process in the cavities is especially difficult, severe complications (orbital, intracranial, sepsis) are often noted. Sinusitis caused by Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, and Proteus are less severe, but they are protracted and often become chronic. Bacterial and viral infection in the adjacent nasal cavities can often pass through the rhinogenic route, through natural openings from the nasal cavity, especially when sneezing,

blowing a hard nose, diving into water, when the pressure in the nasal cavity increases. Infection is also observed to spread by hematogenous route. Infection can spread to the paranasal cavity from the nasal cavity, teeth or other purulent foci, develop after injuries. The development of the disease is caused by bacterial flora, primarily pneumococci, streptococcus, hemophilus influenzae, moraxella, staphylococcus, hemolytic streptococcus, Escherichia coli, gram-positive and gram-negative bacilli, sometimes influenza and parainfluenza viruses, adenoviruses, fungi. The same microflora is often detected in acute sinusitis, and different microflora in chronic sinusitis. The state of local and general immunity is important in the development of the disease.

In infectious diseases (diphtheria, scarlet fever, measles), the infection spreads through the hematogenous way into the nasal cavity.

In 10% of cases, inflammation of the maxillary cavity is caused by the apical granuloma of the low-rooted second and multi-rooted first molars adjacent to the lower wall of the maxillary cavity. In this case, the disease is usually caused by anaerobic microflora, and the discharge has a specific foul smell. In this case, sinusitis is chronic and will disappear only after the damaged tooth is treated.

In chronic diseases of the nasal cavity, the fluid production and transport activity of the mucociliary organ of the mucous membrane is disturbed. The closing of the natural openings of the paranasal sinuses due to swelling of the mucous membrane makes it difficult to remove the pathological discharge from the paranasal sinuses, as a result of which it accumulates in the cavity.

Due to the adverse effects of the environment (gas, dust, pollution with harmful substances), the activity of the cells of mucus-producing glands and the movement of floating epithelial hairs decrease (mucociliary clearance). In turn, this situation leads to the development of an inflammatory process in the nose and nasal cavities.

Classification. B.S. Preobrazhensky (V.T. Palchun, 1974) proposed the following classification of inflammation of the paranasal sinuses:

- A. Exudative form: 1) catarrhal, 2) serous, 3) purulent;
- B. Productive form: 1) wall hyperplastic; 2) with polyposis;
- V. Alterative form: 1) atrophic, 2) necrotic, 3) cholesteatoma, 4) caseous;
- G. Mixed form (purulent-polyposis, cystic-necrotic);
- D. Vasomotor and allergic sinusitis.

Diagnosis. A patient with a disease of the paranasal sinuses undergoes the following examinations:

In recent years, such modern radiological examinations have made it possible to examine the complex structures of the nose and paranasal cavities. In practice, the wide use of equipment such as rigid and flexible optical equipment (endoscope, fiberscope and microscope) with different viewing angles in children's practice enables early detection of ENT diseases.

For a long time, only X-ray or MSCT methods were used to detect inflammation of the nasal cavity. Currently, another modern way to check BYoBs is ultrasound diagnostics. One of these methods is echosinusography. Echosinusography made it possible to abandon X-ray studies that negatively affect the health of patients. The Sinuskan diagnostic device, which is developed by scientists and uses the method of ultrasound endoscopy in its work, is absolutely safe. There is no indication against its use. Sinusography is possible even if the patient is a child under the age of three or a pregnant woman with particularly weak health. Sinuskan-201 allows you to carry out

several diagnostics and adjust the treatment process in time. In this case, the risk of side effects is completely eliminated.

Clinical signs. Clinical symptoms of the disease depend on the clinical form of sinusitis. Patients with this disease, children, have low self-esteem, quality of life and work activities, including difficulties in the educational process, mild colds, and later this condition is accompanied by an increase in body temperature and pain in the whole body, signs of intoxication, tears, runny nose according to the period of the disease, mucous pathological secretions from the nose are observed. Over time, mucous pathological secretions become purulent and put the sick child in a difficult situation, including sharp pains that start from the nose, face and eyes, and then to the ears and head.

Clinical symptoms of the disease depend on the clinical form of sinusitis. In bilateral chronic sinusitis (especially in the form of polyposis), the patient's sense of smell decreases, even anosmia develops. Dryness of the larynx, frequent spitting, large amount of mucus and purulent-mucous sputum discharge in the morning or during the day, nausea remain the main complaints of the patient. The patient's condition will be satisfactory during the period of reduction of the symptoms of the disease.

Pain in the area of the upper jaw cavity is weaker in chronic sinusitis than in acute sinusitis, and it increases during an attack of the disease or when the discharge of the cavity is difficult. The patient's head usually does not hurt when the discharge falls freely into the pharynx; sometimes there is a vague scattered pain in the head; mainly on the affected side, the upper jaw, temple or eye socket, forehead area hurts, sometimes there are signs characteristic of trigeminal neuralgia. The patient's memory is weakened, he cannot concentrate quickly and gets tired quickly.

Due to the constant flow of purulent discharge from the nasal cavity, the skin of the nasal passage becomes inflamed, swollen, and eczema-like changes appear in it. In the front rhinoscopy, the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity is slightly reddened, the nasal conchas are enlarged, a mucous-purulent discharge coming out from under the middle nasal concha and accumulating in the middle and lower nasal passages is visible. When the patient's head is tilted to the opposite side, discharge into the nasal cavity is accelerated. Re-accumulation of pathological discharge after cleaning the middle nasal passage with cotton wrapped around the probe and applying 0.1% naphthyzine or 0.1% adrenaline hydrochloride solution to the mucous membrane is an objective sign of inflammation of the maxillary cavity.

When the extraction of the maxillary cavity is difficult from the front, it flows to the back of the nasal cavity - into the pharynx and is detected during posterior rhinoscopy or mesopharyngoscopy. Chronic granulosa pharyngitis develops in the patient as a result of continuous flow of pathological discharge into the nasopharynx. Purulent discharge from the upper jaw cavity causes inflammation of the mucous membrane of the middle nasal passage, swelling and hypertrophy of the front part of the middle nasal concha; later, polyposis of the front part of the nasal concha may develop in the middle nasal passage.

Treatment. Treatment of chronic rhinosinusitis is carried out conservatively and surgically. Catarrhal and purulent forms of rhinosinusitis give good results when treated conservatively. Treatment is aimed at improving the release of secretions from the affected adjacent cavities, reducing inflammation and increasing the body's defenses.

Currently, early diagnosis of children with CRS, improvement of the quality of treatment, effective elimination of pathogenic infection, scientific justification of rehabilitation methods,

development of pathogenetic mechanisms of damage to other organs and systems, justification of the level of risk factors, determination of clinical characteristics, as well as conservative and minimally invasive improvement of surgical procedures, improvement of methods of prevention of functional sinus surgery and subsequent complications are being carried out.

Immunological disorders and endotoxemia are the main causes of unsatisfactory results in the treatment of chronic rhinosinusitis, and the causes of complications are unclear. Despite the many proposed methods, there are still no clear and reliable grounds for the application of one or another treatment method, and it is difficult to evaluate their effectiveness due to different methodological approaches to the obtained results. Based on the above, it is important and relevant to study the clinical and pathogenetic factors of CRS in order to improve treatment approaches aimed at eliminating the focus of chronic infection and intoxication in CRS.

In order to eliminate the pathological swelling in the BYoBs and to restore the ventilation process in the nose, the method provided by scientists is washing the BYoBs in the Proetts method, simultaneously sanitizing the space and introducing the necessary drugs into the space, cleaning the space with antiseptic drugs, cleaning the pathological masses as much as possible, air circulation in the space leads to improvement, a sharp decrease in the clinical symptoms of the disease, the inherent negative aspects of this method are not denied in exudative forms of chronic sinusitis, the affected spaces are punctured or probed. The upper jaw cavity is punctured through the lower nasal passage under local anesthesia. The puncture needle of Kulikov is directed to the outer corner of the eye on this side and inserted into the side wall of the nose 1.5 cm from the lower nasal concha. Puncture is also a diagnostic method that simultaneously determines the nature of the exudate and the volume of the cavity.

Although every observed patient is treated with maximum conservative treatment, it is necessary to choose the correct surgical direction in time based on the principle of not harming the patient, study the indications and contraindications for surgical procedures in detail, and develop the appropriate sequence of the algorithm. According to it, this is an indication for a combination of surgery, when conservative treatments are useless or ineffective, when the patient's clinical and paraclinical indicators do not change in a positive direction, pathological derivatives, including cystic and polyposis-derived processes and their protracted course, indicated medical and minor palliative intervention, (BYoB probing and puncture procedures), failure to observe adequate dynamic improvement in the patient, as well as frequent recurrence of the disease during the year and the occurrence of cases of SRS, serve as the basis for the use of surgical methods in separate processes.

In order to prevent liquid from entering the respiratory tract, the patient sits with his head tilted forward during the injection of disinfectant solutions.

Antibiotics can be transferred from the nasal cavity to adjacent cavities during "washing" by the Proetz method. With the patient lying on the top, with the head hanging to the maximum, turned 45° to the affected side, after anemization of the nasal passages with adrenaline, an antibiotic solution is injected into the affected nasal cavity using a syringe. An electric aspirator is inserted into the second nostril, which dilutes the air in the nasal cavity and adjacent spaces. At this time, the child says "ku-ku", as a result of which the soft palate closes the nasopharynx and the antibiotic solution enters the cavity where the pathological secretions have appeared. Antibiotic selection is based on the resistance of microorganisms. Non-puncture treatment of inflamed

paranasal sinuses with the help of sinus catheter was developed by G.I. Markov and V.S. Kozlov (1986).

The entrance to the nose of the hoana is closed with an inflated balloon. Then, by sucking air through the channel, the catheter creates negative pressure in the nasal cavity. When there are contraindications to puncture or probing (for example, patients with hematological and severe neurological pathologies), sinus catheter treatment is the method of choice.

If, in combination with other methods of treatment, there is no improvement after washing the cavities several times (up to 10), surgical intervention is considered. Treatment of chronic frontitis after opening the nasal passages (after removal of polyps, resection of the anterior end of the middle nasal concha) is aimed at improving the separation of the cavity by probing the forehead cavity through the forehead-nasal canal.

Chronic sphenoiditis is treated with direct probing of the main cavity under local anesthesia through its natural opening under the control of a microscope or fiberscope, washing and injecting drugs there. During the treatment, that is, up to 2 weeks, the drainage tube is fixed to the natural opening of the cavity.

On the basis of hyposensitizing (hormonal in severe cases) treatment, polyposis and polyposis-purulent sinusitis are treated locally by polypotomy. An endonasal polypotomy is performed using metal wire or soft nose hooks, trying to remove the polyp along with the peduncle as much as possible.

Conservative treatment methods of chronic rhinosinusitis in children's practice should preserve all protective and adaptive mechanisms of the disease in patients as much as possible, and the use of treatment procedures at a level that does not harm the patient and internal organs. In the treatment of CRS, drugs that narrow blood vessels and restore breathing are prescribed in the form of drops and sprays to reduce the obstructive processes in the nasal passages, reduce the size of the nasal concha and open the nasal passages. After removing the visible parts of the polyps, at the last stage of the operation, the polyps in the deep, invisible parts of the nasal cavity are removed under the endoscope and burned using cryo- or laser. The result of such operations is better, because it achieves more rehabilitation.

The maxillary cavity is opened in different ways: endonasal through the lower nasal passage or with an external approach through the lungi fold. In children under 7 years of age, in order not to injure the rudiments of teeth, the cavity is opened endonasally or by resection of the front part of the middle nasal concha with the help of a trocar, after pushing it to the nasal septum and the top, the pathological substrate is removed under optical control and the natural opening is opened.

Thus, in conclusion, it should be noted that the diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the nose and paranasal cavities in children should be done in a unique way, taking into account their age-appropriate anatomical development, the need for early diagnosis, as well as the rapid spread of the process in them, the rapid formation of ocular and cranial complications, taking and applying the necessary measures in time is of particular importance.

Based on the above, further improvement of conservative and surgical treatment methods aimed at eliminating the focus of chronic infection in CRS, preventing complicated forms of the disease and eliminating secondary infection, as well as wide application and promotion of approaches to the problem of CRS, which are still relevant in scientific research, in children's

practice with a new direction we found it necessary to do and focused our scientific work in this direction.

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